

A Selective Fluorescence Spot Test for the Detection of TCA in Soil and Water

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There is a growing interest in methods of analysis for monitoring trichloroacetic acid (TCA) in environmental samples. Gas chromatography¹ and thin layer chromatography and ion-pair reversed phase tlc² methods are used for the analysis of TCA in environmental samples. Feigl³ described a spot-test for the detection of TCA. It is based on the formation of yellow-greenish fluorescent salicylaldazine under uv-light. An attempt has been made here to extend Feigl's fluorescence test with modified procedures for analysing TCA in environmental samples.

Aqueous or ethanolic solutions of the test substances (1%) were used; where a 1% solution could not be prepared, saturated solutions were used. Hydrazine sulphate (10 g) and sodium acetate (10 g) were boiled in distilled water (100 ml), then cooled, filtered and the clear solution was used as the reagent. The indicator paper was made by impregnating Whatman No. 1 filter paper with the reagent. The capillary detector was made by fixing a cotton plug, impregnated with the reagent, in a glass capillary. Aqueous sodium hydroxide (20%) and ethanolic phenol (5%) were used.

The fertile soil sample was composed of sand 32.68%, silt 57.00%, clay 10.06%, organic matter 0.61%, CEC 16.00 meq/100 g and pH 7.75. The pond soil sample was composed of sand 61.00%, silt 25.00%, clay 14.00%, organic matter 2.2%, CEC 7.60 meq/100 g and pH 9.2. The red soil sample was composed of sand 70.82%, silt 16.70%, clay 12.80%, organic matter 0.28%, CEC 3.50 meq/100 g and pH 5.7. The river water sample was composed of dissolved oxygen 8.2–8.7 ppm, total hardness 122–141 ppm, total alkalinity 174–189.4 ppm, chlorides 9.2–9.9 ppm, sulphates 0.42–0.47 ppm, BOD 5.2–5.61 ppm, COD 6.5–6.7 ppm and pH 8.7–8.8. The tube-well water sample was composed of dissolved oxygen 8.0 ppm, total hardness 133–144 ppm, chlorides 13–14 ppm, sulphates 14–18.5 ppm and pH 7.5–7.6. The analyses of soils⁴ and water⁵ were performed by the reported procedures.

Detection in solution: The ethanolic test solution (0.1 ml) was mixed with NaOH solution (2–3 drops) and phenol solution in a micro test tube. The mixture was heated at 100° in a water-bath for 2 min, then cooled and one drop of the reagent was added to it. The mixture was neutralised with acetic acid and then shaken with diethyl ether (0.5 ml). The ethereal layer was spotted on a strip of filter paper, dried and exposed to uv-light of 366 nm.

A greenish-yellow stain on a purple background indicated the presence of TCA.

Detection on indicator paper: A mixture of ethanolic test solution (1 drop), and solutions of NaOH and phenol was evaporated to dryness in a micro-beaker. The indicator paper was placed on the mouth of the beaker and covered with a watch-glass. The contents of the beaker were heated at 180±2° for 5 min and the indicator paper was exposed to uv-light of 366 nm. A greenish-yellow fluorescence indicated the presence of TCA.

Detection in capillary detector: The procedure was the same as above except that capillary detector was used instead of indicator paper.

Detection of TCA in soil: An ethanolic solution of TCA (1.0 ml, 0.1%) was added dropwise with continuous shaking to the soil sample (100 g). The treated soil was divided into five equal portions. After a fixed period of time, TCA was detected in the above soil samples by the following procedure. The treated soil sample (20 g) was taken in a glass column (10 mm i.d.) with glass wool support and TCA was eluted with methanol (20 ml) at the rate of 0.5 ml min⁻¹. The solvent was evaporated by hot air and TCA was detected in the residue by the procedures mentioned above.

Detection of TCA in water: Standard solutions of TCA of different concentrations (10–0.1 ppm) were prepared in distilled water. The lower limit of the detection of TCA was determined in 0.1 ml of the above solutions. Similarly, the lower limit of detection was determined in tap water and river water.

A standard solution of TCA (1 g dm⁻³) was prepared in ethanol which was further diluted (TCA 0.4 ppm) with distilled water. A portion of this solution (50 ml) was extracted with diethyl ether (20 ml) and the layers were separated. Three more fresh portions (each of 50 ml) of the above TCA solution were treated similarly with the same 20 ml of diethyl ether in order to preconcentrate TCA. Finally ether was removed from the extract and the residue was dissolved in methanol (1 ml) and then TCA was detected in 0.1 ml of it. Hence the lower limit of detection was found to be 10 µg/0.1 ml or 0.4 ppm.

Several organic and inorganic compounds were detected by the procedures under study. The following compounds gave positive response. The colour of the fluorescence produced (B≡blue, D≡dark,

G≡green, Y≡yellow) is given in first parenthesis and the lower limit of detection in μg by the procedures (i), (ii) and (iii) are given in order in second parenthesis as first, second and third places respectively: chloroform (YG) (100, 80, 200), 2,4-D (DY) (80, 80, 100), salicylic acid (YG) (50, 50, 60), salicylaldehyde (YG) (30, 20, 30), salicylamide (BG) (50, 50, 50), 2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2, 4, 5-T) (DY) (100, 100, 100) and vanillin (BG) (40, 40, 50). The following compounds did not give positive response and they do not interfere: acetic, ascorbic, benzoic, cinnamic, citric, gallic, indole-3-acetic, indole-3-propionic, maleic, malic, melonic, oxalic and tartaric acids; butanol, ethanol, methanol, methyl-1-butanol and propanol; aniline, diethanolamine, diphenylamine and toluenediamine; acetic, phthalic and succinic anhydrides; dextrose, glucose, starch, sucrose; acetone, acetophenone, ethyl acetate, ethyl formate; petroleum ether, diethyl ether, heterocyclic compounds, barbituric acid, indole, pyridine, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, cyclohexane, nitrobenzene and toluene; aldrin, BHC, dalapon, α - and β -naphthaleneacetic, β -naphthoxyacetic and phenoxyacetic acids, catechol, hydroquinone, phenol, pyrogallol, resorcinol, urea, thiourea, sodium bicarbonate, calcium carbonate, sodium carbonate, ammonium chloride, sodium chloride, ammonium nitrate, sodium nitrate, sodium nitrite, barium sulphate, calcium sulphate, magnesium sulphate, sodium sulphate, potassium hydrogen phosphate; bleaching powder, detergent, soap, lemon juice and tomato juice.

The limits of detection of TCA in soil and water are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - LIMIT OF DETECTION OF TCA IN SOIL AND WATER

Samples	Lower limit of detection (μg) and fluorescence colour observed by different procedures		
	(i)	(ii)	(iii)
Soils :			
Fertile soil	(40)-YG	(30)-YG	(50)-YG
Pond soil	(30)-YG	(30)-YG	(50)-YG
Red soil	(80)-YG	(50)-YG	(100)-YG
Waters :			
Distilled water	(40)-YG	(40)-YG	(50)-YG
River water	(50)-YG	(40)-YG	(50)-YG
Tap water	(40)-YG	(30)-YG	(40)-YG

* (i)≡Detection in solution, (ii)≡detection on indicator paper, (iii)≡detection in capillary detector; YG≡greenish yellow.

The results show that chloroform, salicylic acid, salicylaldehyde and TCA gave greenish yellow, 2,4-D and 2,4,5-T gave dark yellow and salicylamide and vanillin gave blue-green fluorescence. Thus their selective detection can be made in presence of several organic and inorganic compounds listed above. Possible interference due to chloroform can be eliminated by heating the test material to expel the solvent. The greenish yellow fluorescence with salicylic acid and blue-green fluorescence with salicylamide and vanillin are in accordance to the results reported by Feigl³, i.e. salicylic ester saponifies with sodium hydroxide to sodium salicylate that gave blue-violet fluorescence on indicator paper. Table 1 shows that the test can be used for the detection of traces of TCA (30–50 μg) in some of the environmental samples. However, test fails to detect TCA in leaves, lemons and seeds. It may be due to the consumption of TCA in precipitation of proteins or chlorosis. The test can be used successfully for detecting persistence of TCA in different soils. It is found that TCA persists in fertile soil, pond soil and red soil for 6, 8 and 4 days respectively.

The test can be successfully applied for the detection of traces of TCA (30–50 $\mu\text{g}/0.1$ ml) in soil and water. It can be used to detect TCA at ppm level in water by coupling with a suitable preconcentration method (extraction etc.)⁶. The capillary detector is very useful for detecting TCA without removing the matrix, such as soil and organic matter.

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